

RESEARCH ON THE STRENGTH AND WEAR RESISTANCE CHARACTERISTICS OF AIRCRAFT ARTILLERY WEAPON BARRELS

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Annotation: This article provides information on the materials used in the manufacture of aviation artillery barrels, the features of their manufacture, and ways to increase the durability of barrels.

Keywords: barrel, aviation artillery, materials science, barrel materials, production technologies, and durability indicators.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена информация о материалах, используемых при изготовлении стволов авиационной артиллерии, особенностях их производства и способах повышения прочности стволов.

Ключевые слова: ствол, авиационная артиллерия, материаловедение, материалы для стволов, технологии производства и показатели прочности.

Annatsiya: Ushbu maqolada aviatsiya artilleriya qurollari stvollarining tayyorlashda foydalaniladigan materiallar, ularni tayyorlashdagi o'ziga xosliklar va stvollar chidamliligini oshrish yo'llari haqida ma'lumotlar keltrilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: stvol, aviatsiya artilleriya qurollari, materialshunoslik, stvol materiallari, ishlab chiqarish texnologiyalari va chidamlilik ko'rsatgichlari.

Barrels of various guns and small arms are operated under different atmospheric and climatic conditions by military personnel with varying levels of training. Therefore, a variety of materials and processing technologies are used in their manufacture

Requirements for barrels are divided into common and specific categories and differ significantly depending on the combat purpose of the weapon, its installation on a vehicle, and its caliber. The barrel is the most heavily loaded component of a weapon and has a considerably shorter service life than all other assemblies and parts of the weapon. Factors affecting weapon and artillery barrels, materials used for barrel manufacturing, and methods of their processing are discussed [1].

There are both identical requirements for small arms barrels and their operating conditions, as well as specific ones depending on the type. The identical requirements include strength, reliability, firing accuracy, durability, and ergonomics. The specific requirements include low production cost, high manufacturability for combat weapon barrels, high shot grouping accuracy for automatic service and combat weapons, minimum weight, various special requirements for service weapons, high thermal conductivity for automatic combat weapons, etc. It should be taken into account that the most important barrel characteristics—durability and firing accuracy—depend on maintenance service, which can be well organized for sporting, hunting, service, and combat weapons in peacetime, but may significantly deteriorate in wartime for a number of reasons. Thus, barrels, at least those of combat weapons, should be simple, robust, and easy to maintain.

Requirements for artillery gun barrels may also differ significantly depending on the combat purpose of the weapon (field, anti-tank, anti-aircraft, fortress, coastal defense), the type of mounting on military transport (airborne, tank-mounted, naval, railway-mounted, self-propelled), as well as the barrel caliber.

Summarizing the most destructive effects on artillery gun barrels and small arms, the following main factors can be identified:

- friction between the projectile or bullet and the barrel rifling;
- short-term pressure of propellant gases during charge detonation in both longitudinal and transverse directions;
- erosive wear of the barrel bore as a result of firing;
- chemical interaction of powder combustion products with the metal of the barrel walls, intensified by high temperature;
- environmental effects such as moisture, heat, cold, light, dust, sand, low and high pressure, radiation, and other similar factors [2–5].

Let us consider some materials used for the manufacture of small arms barrels.

Bronze is an alloy of copper with tin, as well as other components - excluding zinc and nickel—based on copper. Due to its high toughness, bronze is a very reliable material that resists rupture in an overstressed barrel. Bronzes are relatively insensitive to harmful environmental factors. This metal is not an expensive material; moreover, worn-out barrels can be sent for remelting and new barrels can be produced at minimal cost. However, in modern barrel manufacturing, bronzes are rarely used due to their low strength and hardness, which limits their use with ammunition that generates high gas pressure upon firing. They are mainly used in the assembly of multilayer barrels, which include bronze tubes and a steel bore.

Titanium alloys, while having high strength, are characterized by low density and are non-magnetic. However, their high cost, poor machinability, low heat resistance, and high reactivity when interacting with propellant gases make these alloys poorly suitable for the manufacture of barrels for various types of weapons.

Special heat-resistant alloys based on cobalt, alloyed with nickel, chromium, molybdenum, and iron, possess high heat resistance and thermal stability, but they have not been widely adopted due to the high cost of their components, and these alloys are extremely difficult to machine.

Aluminum alloys (such as silumin, duralumin, etc.) have not found application due to their low mechanical properties, in particular low tensile strength, elastic modulus, heat resistance, as well as poor thermal stability.

Composite materials, representing various combinations of steel, plastic, ceramics, etc., are characterized by low weight, resistance to erosion by propellant gases, and low detectability by metal detectors [7]. The disadvantages of such materials include low thermal conductivity, high cost, and low impact toughness (in the case of ceramic barrels—difficulty in manufacturing and poor maintainability), which has determined their field of application—not for barrels of mass-produced military weapons, but for weapons used by special services.

At present, steels of various chemical compositions are considered the best materials for resisting the full range of adverse effects on barrels. Steels are not expensive materials, are sufficiently technologically suitable for mass production, do not contain scarce components, and, if necessary, are repairable in field conditions.

Classic steels used for small arms barrels are grades 50 and 50RA. The following steel grades are also used: 30KHN2MFA, 30KHRA (this steel, in particular, is used to manufacture barrels for the AK family of assault rifles), 30KHMA, and 38KHMA [8].

In practice, corrosion-resistant steel such as A20KH13 is also used. However, it is not suitable for mass-produced combat weapons due to its low thermal conductivity and relatively low strength properties. Barrels made of corrosion-resistant steels are installed only on hunting rifles.

The choice of materials for barrel manufacturing is also determined by their manufacturability during processing. Since most small arms and barrel artillery are equipped with rifled barrels, the material must be well suited for both pressure forming and machining. At present, the following processing methods are the most widely used [13–16].

Cutting (machining) is the most precise method of barrel manufacturing; it allows obtaining an almost ideal internal geometry of the bore in terms of lands and grooves. However, it is relatively time-consuming (the processing time for one barrel is from 2 to 8 hours).

Rotary forging is a very fast method (about 3 minutes per barrel), which makes it possible to produce barrels with a good internal surface and sufficient accuracy for most applications. The disadvantage of this method is the extremely high cost of the equipment.

Button rifling (broach pulling) is the process of pulling a hard-alloy head (a mandrel) through the barrel bore. The head has a specific profile corresponding to the caliber, number, and twist rate of the rifling. The broaching operation itself takes from one minute to several tens of minutes; however, it requires very careful preparation, primarily in terms of the final bore dimensions, its cleanliness, and lubrication.

After mandrel pulling, the bore becomes slightly larger than the target caliber. To achieve precise dimensions and relieve internal stresses, the barrel is placed in a special furnace, where it is slowly heated and cooled over approximately 50 hours. The disadvantage of this method is the difficulty of selecting the appropriate thermal mode to obtain a barrel with the required final dimensions.

Electrochemical etching involves pulling an electrode with the profile of the rifling through the barrel bore and applying an electric current. At the point of contact, the barrel metal is etched away, forming the rifling. This method is fairly accurate and fast, but it is not applicable to all types of steels.

Modern trends in improving the technology of manufacturing artillery barrels can be clearly observed in the example of tank guns, for which the issues of increasing the destructive capability against moving and stationary armored or fortified targets are particularly urgent. This is achieved by increasing the muzzle velocity of the projectile, as well as by reducing the weight of the gun in order to lighten and reduce the volume of the turret.

In order to reduce barrel warping, a thermal protective sleeve is used, which also performs a number of other functions. Thus, the use of high-rigidity composites contributes to aiming accuracy and reduces dynamic stresses associated with the high velocity of the projectile. The composite sleeve also serves to reduce the radar signature of the tank and conceals the barrel heated after firing from detection by infrared guidance systems of enemy anti-tank weapons.

Modern muzzle brake design requires it to form a single unit with the barrel; therefore, the high-strength steel used for barrel manufacturing must be.

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